

The Bureaucratic Challenge (1988): English Translation of a Historical Commentary on Governance in Algeria

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Abstract

This document presents an English translation of *The Bureaucratic Challenge*, an article originally published by Abdelouahab Zaatri in *Algérie-Actualité* (No. 1197, 22–28 September 1988), shortly before the October 1988 events in Algeria. The text offers a contemporaneous critique of bureaucratic practices, institutional resistance to reform, and the dynamics of influence within public organizations in late-1980s Algeria. The purpose of this translation is not to reinterpret the original article through contemporary theoretical frameworks but to make a historical primary source accessible to a wider international audience. As such, this document contributes to the archival preservation and dissemination of political commentary produced during a significant period of Algerian history.

Keywords: Algeria, bureaucracy, governance, public administration, October 1988, political history, institutional reform.

Historical Note

The article translated below was originally written and published in September 1988, shortly before the social and political upheavals of October 1988 in Algeria. It reflects the author's observations and concerns at the time and should therefore be understood within its historical context.

The translation seeks to preserve the substance and tone of the original French text while adapting certain expressions for clarity in contemporary English. No substantive modifications have been made to the author's argument.

- **Original source:** Zaatri, A. (1988). "Le défi bureaucratique." *Algérie-Actualité*, No. 1197, 22–28 September 1988.
- *The article was subsequently republished by Le Matin d'Algérie on 10 October 2013 in connection with the twenty-fifth anniversary of the October 1988 events.*

Author's Note

Although written in 1988, this text is republished and translated in 2026 because the issues it discusses—bureaucratic inertia, institutional accountability, and governance under constraint—remain relevant to contemporary debates in public administration and political governance. The document is presented as a historical source rather than as a retrospective analysis.

The Bureaucratic Challenge (1988)

Abdelouahab Zaatri

Originally published in Algérie-Actualité, No. 1197, 22–28 September 1988.

When a country's economic circumstances call for change, the momentum of that change inevitably encounters resistance. I do not dispute that bureaucracy is a product of underdevelopment and of the routine functioning of public enterprises. However, viewed in its broader context, it becomes a permanent strategy through which a bureaucratic corporation—that is, a group of individuals occupying positions of varying importance within public enterprises—subtly seeks to establish itself as a countervailing power to government policy.

Its objective is to ensure its own survival and to safeguard both acquired and anticipated advantages. Through bureaucratic practices rooted in administrative formalism, it undermines our institutions while presenting itself as an authority above them, conveying to workers the message that rights do not truly exist and that only the favours granted by bureaucrats are available to them.

Moreover, solidarity among bureaucrats has never been more evident than since it was identified as a significant factor in the dysfunction of both public enterprises and the national economy. The cohesion of this group—which reflects the degree of complacency and mutual complicity among its members—is manifested partly through the informal professional networks that bind them together and entirely through the reciprocal obligations that facilitate access to comfortable or influential positions, whether deserved or otherwise.

This state of affairs is the product of influence peddling, which bureaucrats seek to normalize. Yet it remains an exploitation of the moral authority of public enterprises for strictly personal purposes. It enables them to expand their sphere of influence in order, first, to preserve their privileges and advantages regardless of their actual managerial or administrative competence and, second, to advance through patronage toward the realization of long-standing ambitions of power and status without personal investment or risk.

For this reason, any demand for transparency is immediately perceived as a threat by those who form part of the bureaucratic apparatus. In such circumstances, intimidation becomes the preferred means of encouraging self-censorship, while abuse of authority is readily adopted as a mechanism of self-preservation.

Appeals through internal channels generally amount to little more than one bureaucratic layer referring matters to another. Appeals pursued outside the organization are frequently met with attempts—subtle or otherwise—to invalidate the complaint and, in some cases, to retaliate against those who raised it.

Finally, it must be emphasized that any pressure, manoeuvre, or Machiavellian practice designed to conceal abuses of authority or the neglect of human and material resources within public enterprises—whether through traditional methods or more sophisticated techniques intended to avoid suspicion—is contrary to sound economic management.

Such situations reveal the very foundations of the bureaucratic environment. It seeks to function as a closed system and ultimately consists of little more than the preservation of vested interests, opportunism, entrenched habits, and the rejection of fair competition in favour of personal connections, compliance, and servility.

Translation and Republication Statement

The present English version was prepared and republished by the author for academic, historical, and archival dissemination. The objective is to make a contemporaneous document from 1988 accessible to a broader international audience while preserving its original meaning and historical context.

The translation seeks to remain faithful to the substance and tone of the French text. Apart from minor linguistic adaptations required for clarity in English, no substantive changes have been made to the original argument.

This document is presented as a historical source and should be interpreted within the political, economic, and institutional context of Algeria in 1988.

Citation

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